

ISic3101

I.Sicily inscription 3101

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331427

1. ὑπ(ατία) Φή[λικος καὶ Φλ(αβίου)]

2. Τα[ύρου τῶν λαμ(προτάτων)]²⁷ Φή[λικος καὶ] | Τα[ύρου λαμ(προτάτων)]²⁷.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645449

PHI 331427

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0876

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 18 no.59

Ferrua, A 1946-1947. Florilegio d'iscrizioni paleocristiane di Sicilia. *Rendiconti della Pontifica accademia romana di archeologia*. 22: 227-239. At 227 no.1

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